

THE EMERGENCE OF KARAKALPAK JOURNALISM IN THE XX CENTURY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6506308>

Islambek Abiev

islambek.abiev@gmail.com

Master of Karakalpak State University

Abstract: *This article mentions the information about the emergence of Karakalpak press during the period of the USSR. Moreover, it points out the problems revealed in the process of maintaining the first publication newspaper, "Erkin Karakalpak". In addition to this, the research article kicks off the other data about the newborn newspapers, which were dedicated to the specific auditory of readers.*

Key words: *journalism, press, USSR, the Executive Committee of the Amudarya, Interim Executive Committee of the USSR, Karakalpak Autonomous Region, Erkin Karakalpak, Miynetkesh Karakalpak.*

Studying Uzbek journalism, especially publishing, sheds light on the processes of information dissemination in the pre- and post-independence period, on the formation of public opinion, as well as on socio-economic, spiritual and educational processes, and, of course, the analysis of periodical publications of that time is essential. This is because newspapers can serve as a historical source that preserves the social events of their time.

In my current scientific work, I would like to explore the above points through an analysis of the local press of the Autonomous Republic of Karakalpakstan, located in the northwest of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In the first half of the 20th century, the Soviet system had to establish a social, economic and spiritual link between society and the government in order to influence mass consciousness and change the traditional way of life and thinking of society. It is no secret that as society develops, its need for information increases. Therefore, the establishment of new publishing houses on the territory of Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan, was essential to spread their influence and strengthen the ideological impact on the mentality of the masses, which had developed over the centuries.

On June 11, 1918, the Trade Union of Journalists of the Republic of Turkestan was founded in Tashkent. "Nasha gazeta" (Our Newspaper), "Izvestiya" (Information), "Turkestanskaya Pravda" (Truth of Turkistan), "Ishtirokiun" (Participant), "Qızıl bayraq" (Red Flag), "Turkistan", "Krasnyy front" (Red Front) and

other newspapers started their work. The first journalists such as: N.Torequlov, T.Ryskulov, B.Dadabaev, I.Khidiraliev, K.Atabaev, A.Rakhimbaev, I.Khakimbaev, M.Yuldoshkhoriev, L.Alimi, N.Enikeev, U.Emonkhujayev and others actively participated in the operation of the press with their articles.

In June 1919 the newspaper "Izvestia", the organ of the Executive Committee of the Amudarya branch, was established in the city of Turtkul, the Amudarya region, the Republic of Turkistan. I.Brikman, I.Kosyanenko and P.Baranovskiy also published their journalistic materials in this organ .

In September 1921, by the decision of the regional executive committee, the name of the newspaper "Izvestia" was changed to "Красный Амударьинец" (Red Amudarya), and in 1922 it was renamed again to "Амударьинская жизнь" (Life of Amudarya) .

So, it can be considered as the first newspaper published in Russian language on the territory of Karakalpakstan. Unfortunately, it is impossible to find the copies of the newspaper in the archives because they were destroyed or demolished. This means that the circulation and the copies of the newspaper were few and the newspaper was not readable for the locals as their language was different.

The archives show that in the mid-1920s, two newspapers in Muslim language were published in the region: in Turtkul, the weekly newspaper "Birinshi adym" (First Step) with a circulation of 1000 copies and in Khodjeyli, the newspaper "Erkin Karakalpak" (Independent Karakalpak) with a circulation of 250 copies . However, the publication of newspapers in Karakalpakstan was irregular, mainly for logistical reasons (lack of financial support, fonts, equipment, experienced staff, etc.) .

On October 14, 1924, at the second session of the Interim Executive Committee of the USSR, headed by M.I.Kalinin, the national-state delimitation was discussed, and A. Dosnazarov spoke at the meeting, mentioning not only the hard life of the Karakalpaks and the much slower political-economic development of the region, but also pointing out that "when the Soviet Union came, the nations should show their borders and be economically independent. If the small nations and their development are respected, our multinational government will be strengthened" .

As a result, in 1924, the national independence of the Karakalpak nation was restored as the Karakalpak Autonomous Region (KAR), which brought about a need for radio and press. The publication of a newspaper in the Karakalpak language was necessary to disseminate the decisions of the party and trade unions of the Union Government to the people and to arouse the political activity of them.

On November 18, 1924, the Organizing Bureau of the KAR, headed by A.Dosnazarov, considered the issue of publishing a single regional newspaper. Speaking on the subject, A.Arziev pointed out the need to publish one newspaper as

the organ of the Organizing Bureau, the Revolutionary Committee, the Trade Union and the Koshchi Union. He proposed that this newspaper be called "Erkin Karakalpak" and that the newspaper of the same name in Khodjeyli be closed and all ownership transferred to the regional printing house in Turtkul. It was also proposed to appoint A. Kudabaev as Executive Secretary and S. Agaidarov as his deputy .

Surely, it may seem that it was the first step in creating a premier newspaper in the Karakalpak language, however, there were several facts that the publishing house had a number of difficulties in both technical and financial ways. For instance, the first circulation of the newspaper was on December 31st, 1924. Moreover, according to the archive data, the number of copies of each newspaper circulation was 1200 and the business of publishing the newspaper was not manageable as it seemed before. The main reasons for that were the difficult financial situation of the printing house, the lack of equipment, financial resources, types, fonts, paints, as well as competent specialists, correspondents, experienced employees, typesetters. As a consequence, in September 1925, the newspaper had to stop its work after 25 circulations due to the facts mentioned above.

As indisputable evidence, it should be noted that the articles in the first issues of the newspaper had a cultural and educational character, and at the same time, the decisions and news of the regional authorities were published. Moreover, the language of the former circulations of the newspaper was not stable and the same, which means the articles in it were written in Karakalpak, Uzbek, Kazakh, even Arab-Persian. This in turn shows that there was a lack of qualified personnel in the editorial department and that not every article was checked under strict scrutiny. On the pages of the newspaper on June 9th, 1925, which was found in the home archive of Abdusalom Iygilikov from Nukus, understandable phrases like «Иқтсади сиясат күни, худудндағы дийқанларның дйханшлқ етуб турған жйрларина» could be noticed.

Since then, the issue of reorganizing the publication of the newspaper was at the center of several meetings such as at the Organizational Distribution Department of the Kazak Region Committee. And finally, at the beginning of 1926, 10,000 rubles were allocated by the Allied National Fund for the development of the newspaper business, and since the middle of 1926, the publication of the "Erkin Karakalpak" newspaper was resumed .

In my point of view, the main support for the survival of this newspaper was financial help by the government. Another point is that the Karakalpakstan Autonomous Region was 180,000 sq.km. and according to the 1926 census, 38.1% of the population were Karakalpaks, 28.5% Kazakhs, 27.6% Uzbeks, 3.2% Turkmens,

and 2.6% other ethnic groups. This also shows the strong reason for existing a press in the Karakalpak language as most part of the population is Karakalpaks.

We can say without hesitation that in May 1927, P.Barlamov's arrival in the Karakalpak party organization coincided with the period when the newspaper's situation changed for the better. He previously worked as a deputy of the head Agitation and propaganda department of the Kazakh regional party committee in 1924-25 and as a deputy of the head agitation and propaganda department of the Kazkraykom of the CPSU (b) in February 1925-27 .

Thus, the executive secretary of "Erkin Karakalpak" K.Nazaralin stated in his memo of February 18, 1928 that the day of "actual formalisation" of the newspaper should be considered as October 15, 1927 (the spelling is preserved - S.N.). According to him, at that time the number of subscribers increased, their exact number was revealed, the editorial staff was issued .

The archive data show that on August 27, 1928, the Secretariat of the Regional Committee decided to rename the newspaper "Erkin Karakalpak" to "Miynekesh Karakalpak" (Labour Karakalpak). However, only a year later, on November 4, 1929, the decision of the Secretariat was confirmed by the Regional Committee Bureau. On February 23, 1930, the Secretariat of the Regional Committee approved the editorial board of the newspaper "Miynekesh Karakalpak", which included Rakipov, Matyakubov, K. Allabergenov, Koblanova and T. Safiev. The newspaper "Miynekesh Karakalpak" and as its appendix newspaper "Trudovoy Karakalpak" (Labour Karakalpak), which was in Russian, were published since then. By decision of the Executive Committee of the KAR, on August 20, 1931, the newspaper "Labour Karakalpak" was again renamed "Sovetskuyu Karakalpakiyu" (Soviet Karakalpakia), and R. Rustemov was appointed its editor .

By this time, the newspaper's public relations had grown, and its main focus was on agitation and propaganda. It is no secret that the Stalinist process began in the late 1920s and early 1930s, and the struggle against stratification was in full swing. At that time, the government demanded that the people unite and work actively. This, in turn, increased the pressure on the press to shape public opinion.

To sum up, we can say that 1920-1930 was the first small period of the emergence of Karakalpak Publishing House, and during this period the problems that arose in the editorial office were solved, namely:

- an updated material and technical base;
- financial support from the government
- Qualified personnel began to work in the editorial office.

Finally, at that time new kinds of newspapers and magazines appeared such as: "Sovetskaya Karakalpakiya", "Jetkinshek", "Kenes oqitiwshisi", "Jas Leninshi",

“Kommunist”, “Kolxozshi”, “Qizil baliqshi” and these newspapers had its own audience and readers.

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